

NOTE**Distribution and geochemical significance of biphenyls and related bicyclic aromatic structures in oils from Ancon oilfield (Tertiary Progreso Basin), Ecuador**MANUEL MARTÍNEZ,^{1*} ERICA LORENZO,¹ ANTONIO MORATO¹ and ADRIANA GAMBOA²¹Universidad Estatal Península de Santa Elena. 240210 La Libertad, Ecuador²Universidad Politécnica Territorial del Oeste de Sucre. Cumaná 6101, Venezuela*(Received February 12, 2020; Accepted April 28, 2020)*

A set of oils from Ancon oilfield (Neogene Progreso Basin, Ecuador), were studied by GC-MS in terms of the occurrence and distribution of cyclohexylbenzenes, biphenyls, and diphenylmethanes, and their use as indicators of thermal maturity and biodegradation. In the studied oils, biphenyls are more abundant than the other related bicyclics; 3-methylbiphenyl is the most predominant over remnant homologs. A weak correlation between different biphenyl ratios and sensitive parameters for thermal maturity (MPI-1 and %Rc) is observed; probably, the input of terrestrial organic matter could be responsible for the low correlation. The linear correlation between biphenyls and cyclohexylbenzenes is explained through dehydrogenation reactions during oil formation. However, no correlation is observed with diphenylmethanes nor cyclohexylbenzenes. The biodegradation achieved in the studied oils is equal to or less than 3 in the PM scale, according to the negligible effects over the distribution of these compounds, confirmed by aromatic biodegradation indices derived from alkyl-naphthalenes.

Keywords: Ancon, Ecuador, biphenyls, diphenylmethanes, cyclohexylbenzenes

INTRODUCTION

Biphenyls, cyclohexylbenzenes, and diphenylmethanes are important components in the aromatic hydrocarbon fraction of oils and rock extracts. Their relative abundance can reflect differences in the sedimentary environment and/or the type of organic matter (Jiang *et al.*, 2001). Biphenyls have been proposed as precursors of dibenzothiophenes (Asif *et al.*, 2009). Similarly, biphenyls and diphenylmethanes can be precursors of various fluorene derivatives. Both are associated with terrestrial organic matter (Li *et al.*, 2013). Moreover, cyclohexylbenzenes have been proposed as precursors of biphenyls, produced through dehydrogenation reactions (Alexander *et al.*, 2009).

On the other hand, a relationship has been found between the distribution of alkylbiphenyl homologs and the thermal maturity in rock samples (Alexander *et al.*, 1986); other authors have proposed that they are also sensitive, along with alkyl diphenylmethanes, to biodegradation (Trolio *et al.*, 1999).

This work aims to document for the first time the presence of cyclohexylbenzenes, biphenyls and diphenylmethanes in oils from Ancon (Neogene Progreso Basin, southwestern Ecuador), and to discuss their geochemical meaning. Very few geochemical studies have been undertaken on these oils (Lorenzo *et al.*, 2018).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The oil samples (API Gravity 34–44°) come from different active wells in Ancon Field, Miocene Dos Bocas Fm., Progreso Basin, southwestern Ecuador. The geologic framework of the study area was documented elsewhere (Lorenzo *et al.*, 2018). Dried and sediment-free samples were fractionated by column chromatography with activated alumina as a stationary phase into saturates, aromatics and polar compounds (SAR), using *n*-hexane, toluene, and dichloromethane respectively, as eluting solvents. Asphaltene fractions had been previously separated from each crude oil sample by precipitation from a solution containing a 40:1 volumetric excess of *n*-heptane (Trolio *et al.*, 1999; Speight, 2004).

GC-MS analysis of the aromatic fraction was performed on an Agilent 6890 Gas Chromatograph - 5975 Mass Detector, using a 60 m-DB-5 column. The injector temperature was set at 290°C. The oven temperature pro-

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Fig. 1. Fragmentograms of selected ions in the studied oils. A: Combined ions (m/z 154 + 168 + 182) in the aromatic fraction of sample ANC-093, corresponding to biphenyls and diphenylmethanes. The region between 47 and 50 minutes has been enlarged. B: Combined ions (m/z 160 + 174 + 188) in the sample ANC-1121, belonging to alkylcyclohexylbenzenes; shaded signals belong to unidentified methyl- and dimethylcyclohexylbenzenes. The identification of the peaks is indicated in Table 1.

gram was 50°C (2 min) to 300°C (held 70 min) at 2.5°C/min, with helium as a carrier gas. The identification of compounds was based on the NIST Mass Spectral Search Program together with data from the literature (Ogbesejana *et al.*, 2017).

RESULTS

Identification of alkylbiphenyls, alkyldiphenylmethanes, and cyclohexylbenzenes

The chromatographic profile of the summed m/z 154 and 168 fragmentograms (methylbiphenyls, MBP and diphenylmethane, DPM) of the aromatic fraction of one of the oils taken as reference, is shown in Fig. 1(a); the identified compounds are summarized in Table 1. Biphenyl is present in all the analyzed samples and its concentration is much higher than the content of

diphenylmethane; 3-methylbiphenyl (3-MBP) is the most abundant compound of its homologs. Ion m/z 182 fragmentogram is shown in Fig. 1(a) to visualize the different dimethylbiphenyls. The region between 47 and 50 minutes in the fragmentogram has been extended to visualize and identify the different alkylbiphenyls and alkyldiphenylmethanes clearly; only three methyl-diphenylmethanes were detected.

The cyclohexylbenzenes can be detected from m/z 160, 174 and 188 ions (Fig. 1(b)) and recognized by the additional presence of the m/z 104, 105, 117 ions, typical of the fragmentation pattern of these compounds. At least seven of them were identified (Fig. 1(b)).

Relations between biphenyls and cyclohexylbenzenes

The ratios between the structurally similar biphenyls and cyclohexylbenzenes were calculated (Table 2). All the calculated ratios were greater than 1 indicating the predominance of biphenyls over cyclohexylbenzenes and diphenylmethane. Two parameters sensitive to thermal maturity, Methyl Phenanthrene Index (MPI-1) (Radke *et al.*, 1982) and calculated vitrinite reflectance (%R_c) (Radke *et al.*, 1984), were calculated in all samples and included in the table.

DISCUSSION

Genetic correlation between compounds

The structural similarity between biphenyls and cyclohexylbenzenes can be visualized by plotting the ratios between specific homologs of both series of compounds (Figs. 2(a) and (b)). Significant linear correlations indicate that these compounds sharing the same carbon skeletons are genetically related through dehydrogenation reactions during oil formation (Alexander *et al.*, 2009).

Thermal maturity

Biphenyls are sensitive to variations in maturity (Ogbesejana *et al.*, 2017) and the 3-MBP/2-MBP ratio has been proposed as an indicator of thermal history (Alexander *et al.*, 1986). However, only a weak positive correlation was observed between the 3-MBP/2-MBP ratio and MPI-1, which is one of the most robust geochemical ratios of thermal maturity (Radke *et al.*, 1984) (Fig. 2(c)). When the values of the 3-MBP/2-MBP ratio are plotted against %R_c, according to Radke *et al.* (1984) (Fig. 2(e)), the samples do not follow the reported trend lines for biphenyls according to thermal maturity (Alexander *et al.*, 1986). On the other hand, 2'-MCB coelutes with 3'-MCB, so an equivalent relationship with biphenyls cannot be calculated with methylcyclohexylbenzenes. However, the C-4MB/3'-MCB ratio was tested, using the greater relative stability of the para-substituted isomers

Table 1. Aromatic hydrocarbons identified in this study

Peak	Compound	Abbreviation
1	Biphenyl	BP
2	2-methylbiphenyl	2-MBP
3	Diphenylmethane	DPM
4	3-methylbiphenyl	3-MBP
5	4-methylbiphenyl	4-MBP
6	2,3'-dimethylbiphenyl	2,3-DMBP
7	2,5-dimethylbiphenyl	2,5-DMBP
8	2,4- + 2,4'-dimethylbiphenyl	2,4- + 2,4'-DMBP
9	3-methyl-diphenylmethane	3-MDPM
10	2,3-dimethylbiphenyl	2,3-DMBP
11	2-methyl-diphenylmethane	2-MDPM
12	4-methyl-diphenylmethane	4-MDPM
13	3-ethylbiphenyl	3-EBP
14	3,5-dimethylbiphenyl	3,5-DMBP
15	3,3'-dimethylbiphenyl	3,3'-DMBP
16	4-ethylbiphenyl	4-EBP
17	3,4-dimethylbiphenyl	3,4-DMBP
18	4,4'-dimethylbiphenyl	4,4'-DMBP
19	3,4'-dimethylbiphenyl	3,4'-DMBP
20	Cyclohexylbenzene	CB
21	3-methylcyclohexylbenzene	3'-MCB
22	1-methylcyclohexylbenzene	1'-MCB
23	Cyclohexyl-2-methylbenzene + cyclohexyl-3-methylbenzene	C-2MB + C-3MB
24	Cyclohexyl-4-methylbenzene	C-4MB
25	3-methylcyclohexyl-3-methylbenzene	3'-MC-3MB
26	Cyclohexyl-3,5-dimethylbenzene	C-3,5-DMB
27	Cyclohexyl-3,4-dimethylbenzene	C-3,4-DMB

Table 2. The ratios between biphenyls, cyclohexylbenzenes, and diphenylmethanes. MPI-1, %Rc, and TBR were calculated according to Radke et al. (1982); Radke et al. (1984) and Peters et al. (2005), respectively. Shaded boxes correspond to samples with signs of biodegradation.

Sample	BP/DPM	BP/CB	3-MBP/3'-MCB	4-MBP/4'-MCB	3,4-DMBP/C-3,4DMB	3-MBP/2-MCB	MPI-1	%Rc	TBR
ANC-0004	11.25	1.96	6.56	3.61	2.74	12.7	0.71	0.80	4.6
ANC-0019	8.60	1.99	6.97	3.20	2.12	9.0	0.61	0.73	4.5
ANC-0093	16.87	4.09	11.56	5.26	3.93	16.9	0.80	0.85	4.5
ANC-0106	9.25	3.90	10.07	4.25	1.85	17.3	0.68	0.78	4.6
ANC-0446	13.60	2.27	7.38	3.96	3.60	11.8	0.91	0.91	4.7
ANC-0452	—	1.38	14.45	4.76	2.76	13.3	0.76	0.83	5.1
ANC-0781	6.02	1.11	3.58	2.21	1.52	5.7	0.36	0.59	4.1
ANC-1013	12.56	1.27	4.86	3.15	2.44	8.1	0.69	0.79	5.2
ANC-1121	16.05	1.85	6.45	3.69	3.12	9.8	0.76	0.83	4.7
ANC-1254	9.91	2.00	6.52	3.19	2.74	14.1	0.69	0.83	4.6
ANC-1440	11.16	1.46	5.47	3.18	2.12	10.4	0.81	0.86	4.5
ANC-1863	13.23	2.50	9.23	5.43	7.05	12.6	0.88	0.90	5.1

to the meta-positions as a criterion (Fig. 2(d)). Both graphs show a lack of correlation between the distribution of biphenyls, or cyclohexylbenzenes with thermal maturity.

The geochemical characteristics of the studied oils (Pri/Phy, Pri/*n*-C₁₇ and Phy/*n*-C₁₈ ratios; steranes and isotopic distribution) matches with mixed organic matter in reducing to slight oxidant conditions (Lorenzo *et al.*, 2018), in agreement with the estuarine depositional setting proposed for Dos Bocas Fm. (Cobos, 2010). The in-

put of terrestrial organic matter could be responsible for the absence of a clear correlation between biphenyls and thermal maturity. The genesis of these bicyclic ring systems might occur through phenol coupling of precursor compounds at oxidizing conditions. However, the provenance of the biphenyls is not yet clear; a relationship between the type of organic matter and the content of biphenyls has not been clearly demonstrated (Ogbesejana *et al.*, 2018). The thermal maturity interval in this work

Fig. 2. Relationship between parameters tested. (a): Biphenyl/Cyclohexylbenzene (BP/CB) vs. 3-MBP/3'-MCB; (b): 4-MBP/4'-MCB vs. 3-MBP/3'-MCB. (c): 3-MBP/2-MBP vs. MPI-1. (d): C-4MB/3'-MCB vs. MPI-1. (e): 3-MBP/2-MBP vs. %Rc (Alexander et al., 1986).

Fig. 3. Left: Total ion chromatogram (TIC) of the saturated fraction of samples ANCC004 (pristine) and ANC1121 (biodegraded). Center: m/z 154 + 168 fragmentogram corresponding to biphenyls and diphenylmethane. Right: m/z 160 + 174 fragmentogram corresponding to cyclohexylbenzenes. Pri = pristane; Phy = phytane; $n-C_{22}$ and $n-C_{32}$ = n -alkanes with 22 and 32 carbon atoms, respectively.

is much narrower than that shown by previous studies, which may be making it difficult to appreciate a clear correlation with the parameters tested.

Effect of biodegradation

The comparison of the combined m/z 154 + 168 fragmentogram (B+DPM+MBP) of a non-biodegraded oil (ANC-0004) and a biodegraded one (ANC-1121) was carried out, seeking to detect the effects of biodegradation on the distribution of the studied compounds (Fig. 3). Some ratios between alkyl-naphthalenes, reported as aromatic biodegradation indices (DBR = 1,6-DMN/1,5-DMN -DMN: *dimethylnaphthalene*-; TBR = 1,3,6-TMN/1,2,4-TMN, -TMN: *trimethylnaphthalene*- (Peters *et al.*, 2005)) show minor differences between samples. No changes in the relative distribution of biphenyls or cyclohexylbenzenes are detected, suggesting a level of biodegradation lesser than 4–5 in the PM scale (Trolieo *et al.*, 1999); this result corroborates the level of biodegradation achieved is equal to or less than 3, reported by Lorenzo *et al.* (2018).

CONCLUSIONS

The present paper documents the occurrence, content, and distribution of bicyclic, non-condensed aromatic ring systems in oils from the Ancon field, Tertiary Progreso Basin, southwestern Ecuador. The presence of biphenyls, cyclohexylbenzenes, and diphenylmethanes is described, being 3-MBP the most abundant alkyl biphenyl in all samples. Methyl- and dimethylbiphenyls show a clear positive correlation with homologs methyl- and dimethyl cyclohexylbenzenes. No correlation is found for diphenylmethane. The absence of correlation between biphenyls and MPI-1 or %Rc prevents their use as thermal maturity index in the studied oils; probably, the input of terrestrial organic matter is responsible for this lack of correlation. Cyclohexylbenzenes are insensitive to thermal maturity, as revealed by the C-4MB/3'-MCB ratio. Also, the extent of biodegradation did not reach the level to alter the studied aromatic hydrocarbons.

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